

A rare triple end-on bridges [Ni₄] compound with shortest Ni...Ni separation : Synthesis, characterization, structure and magnetic behaviour[†]

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Abstract : A tetranuclear nickel(II) complex, [Ni₄(L2)₂(N₃)₈(CH₃CN)₂].4CH₃CN (**1**), has been synthesized by employing three end-on ($\mu_{1,1}$ -N₃) azido anions supported by polydentate flexible ligand. The compound has been characterized by analytical and spectroscopic results, along with magnetostructural studies. Single-crystal X-ray diffraction studies suggest that the compound is a rare example of triple end-on ($\mu_{1,1}$ -N₃) azido bridged nickel(II) species, with very short Ni...Ni separation and very low Ni-N-Ni angle with promising ferromagnetic interactions.

Keywords : Flexidentate ligand, tetranuclear nickel(II) complex, triple end-on azido bridge, shortest Ni...Ni separation, synthesis, properties, structure.

Introduction

Polynuclear transition metal coordination compounds, in which spin coupling between the paramagnetic centers present and propagated through either bridging function containing polydentate especially polynucleating ligands and/or through bridging anions, are of significant interest to researchers seeking molecule based magnetic materials displaying interesting electronic and magnetic properties¹. It should also be noted that although a huge number of paramagnetic cluster complexes exhibiting magnetic exchange interactions between metal centres have been reported so far, in only a few are the interactions of ferromagnetic in nature. The achievement of ferromagnetic coupling between metal ions is still an interesting challenge for synthetic chemists not only because of its relative scarcity but also because it leads to high spin ground states, one of the most important requirements for a cluster metal complex to exhibit potential applications as Single-Molecule Magnets (SMMs)², and low temperature magnetic coolers³. The area of molecular magnetism also provided exciting new challenges which appeared on the horizon, including the use of building block approaches for the preparation of complex multifunctional magnetic materials, the nano sized magnetic molecules and other nanostructures that exhibit quantum effects and the rea-

lization of practical applications. In all of these developments, inorganic chemists play a pivotal role⁴. In view of the above considerations, and taking into account that polynuclear transition metal complexes in general exhibit a richer variety of magnetic properties, we decided to use a new neutral hexadentate ligand (with all six nitrogen donors (N₆), Schemes 1 and 2) to prepare metal clusters containing azido bridged groups with presumable high spin ground states. In this paper, we report the synthesis, spectroscopic, structural characterization and promising magnetic properties of a rare triple end-on ($\mu_{1,1}$ -N₃) azido bridged nickel(II) compound, [Ni₄(L2)₂(N₃)₈(CH₃CN)₂].4CH₃CN (**1**), with shortest Ni...Ni separation, and lowest Ni-N-Ni angle.

Experimental

Materials :

All manipulations were performed under aerobic conditions using reagents and solvents as received. Glyoxal, ethylene diamine and pyridine 2-carboxaldehyde and metal salts were obtained from SRL, Merck and Lancaster Chemical Company and were used as received. All other solvents and chemicals were of analytical grade.

Caution! Perchlorate salts, azides, are potentially explosive especially in presence of organic ligands. There-

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of ligand.

Scheme 2. Possible ligand transformation pathways.

fore, these compounds must be handled with care and prepared only in small amounts.

Synthesis of ligand :

The ligand (**L1**) was prepared by consecutive two steps reaction. In the first step glyoxal (0.290 g, 5 mmol) was added to ethylenediamine (0.601 g, 10 mmol) in 1 : 2 mole ratio in dehydrated alcohol. Then the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. Then after cooling the mixture pyridine 2-carboxaldehyde (1.07 g, 10 mmol) was added. Then overall mixture was refluxed for another 6 h. After cool-

ing the additional solvent was evaporated and the ligand was dried in a vacuum desiccator to get solid ligand. Yield : 75%; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{20}N_6$: C, 67.46; H, 6.30; N, 26.20. Found : C, 67.41; H, 6.25; N, 26.16%.

Synthesis of complex :

The ligand (**L1**) (0.080 g, 0.25 mmol) in 10 mL CH_3CN was added to a CH_3CN (10 mL) solution of $Ni(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.182 g, 0.5 mmol), forming a yellow orange solution. Then to this solution NaN_3 (0.065 g, 1 mmol) in (1 mL H_2O + 5 mL CH_3CN) was added. The

mixture was stirred for 0.5 h. The resulting yellow solution was filtered and kept for slow evaporation. After 7 days good bluish-green crystalline compound obtained. Yield : 65%; Anal. Calcd. (for desolvated species) for C₄₀H₄₆N₃₈Ni₄ : C, 37.13; H, 3.59; N, 41.14; Ni, 18.15. Found : C, 37.09; H, 3.51; N, 41.07; Ni, 17.95%; IR : 2123, 2062, 2028, 1608, 1574, 1480, 1387, 1242, 1184, 890, 770, 679, 541 cm⁻¹.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were performed using a Perkin-Elmer 2400II elemental analyzer. Nickel contents were determined gravimetrically as the nickel dimethyl glyoximate complex. IR spectra (as KBr pellets, 4000–400 cm⁻¹) were taken at 298 K using a Shimadzu Model 8400 S spectrophotometer. Magnetic data were obtained with a Quantum Design MPMS SQUID susceptometer. All samples were 3 mm diameter pellets molded from ground crystalline samples. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were performed in the 2–300 K temperature range under a 0.1 T applied magnetic field, and diamagnetic corrections were applied by using Pascal's constants⁵. Isothermal magnetization measurements were performed up to 5 T at 2 K. The magnetic susceptibilities have been computed by exact calculations of the energy levels associated to the spin Hamiltonian through diagonalization of the full matrix with a general program for axial symmetry⁶, and with the MAGPACK program package in the case of magnetization⁷. Least-squares fittings were accomplished with an adapted version of the function-minimization program MINUIT⁸.

X-Ray crystallography :

Single-crystals suitable for X-ray crystallographic analysis was selected following examination under a microscope. The X-ray diffraction data were collected at 296 K with MoK α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073$ Å) using a Bruker Nonius SMART Apex II CCD diffractometer equipped with a graphite monochromator. Intensity data were collected in the ω -2 θ scan mode. The data were corrected for Lorentz, polarization and absorption effects, the latter using SADABS⁹. The structure was solved by direct methods and the structure solution and refinement was based on $|F|^2$. The non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. H-atoms have been calculated and

refined using a riding model, whereas the other H-atoms were localized through difference synthesis. The atomic scattering factors and anomalous dispersion terms were taken from the standard compilation¹⁰. The structure was solved with SHELXS-97 and refined with SHELXL-97 computer programs^{11,12}.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

The new tetranuclear complex containing four nickel(II) atoms [Ni₄(L2)₂(N₃)₈(CH₃CN)₂].4CH₃CN (**1**) has been prepared from the flexible hexadentate ligand as described in Scheme 1 and possible transformation route during synthesis of tetrameric species has been sketched in Scheme 2.

The complex [Ni₄(L2)₂(N₃)₈(CH₃CN)₂].4CH₃CN (**1**) was prepared by the reaction of ligand (**L1**) with Ni(ClO₄)₂.6H₂O along with NaN₃ in a 1 : 2 : 4 molar ratio in aqueous acetonitrile medium under stirring condition. Then the complex was characterized by elemental analyses (C, H, N and metal) and IR spectral data. The complex is neutral in nature. The IR spectrum of **1** exhibit bands corresponding to the asymmetric stretching vibrations of N₃⁻ at 2062 cm⁻¹ and 2028 cm⁻¹ and also exhibit band at 2123 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the terminal N₃⁻. The complex **1** also show a C=N azomethine bands at 1608 and 1574 cm^{-1,13-15}.

Structure of compound 1 :

The tetranuclear molecule include the neutral [Ni₄(L2)₂(N₃)₈(CH₃CN)₂].4CH₃CN (**1**) with two molecules of acetonitrile in asymmetric unit as solvent of crystallization. Fig. 1, showing the [Ni₄(L2)₂(N₃)₈(CH₃CN)₂] molecule and selected bond distances [Å] and bond angles [°] are provided in Table 2. The tetranuclear molecule shows no evidence of any interaction with solvent counterpart.

The tetrameric (Ni₄) units of compound **1** contain two types of hexacoordinated Ni^{II} centers. Ni(1) coordinated by two nitrogens atoms of transformed Schiff base (N₆) ligand (L2) (Scheme 2) as bis(didentate mode), three end-on ($\mu_{1,1}$ -N₃) and sixth coordination site being fulfilled by azido anion as terminal mode of binding. While that of Ni(2) coordinated by two nitrogens transformed hexadentate Schiff base (N₆) ligand (L2) (Scheme 2) bind

Fig. 1. ORTEP plot and labelling scheme for $[\text{Ni}_4(\text{L}2)_2(\text{N}_3)_8(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_2] \cdot 4\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$. Thermal ellipsoids are drawn at 50% probability level and the hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity.

as bis(didentate mode), three end-on ($\mu_{1,1}\text{-N}_3$) and sixth coordination site being fulfilled by solvent acetonitrile molecule. Each tetrameric unit contains two acetonitrile molecules in asymmetric unit as solvent of crystallization. The compound **1** is a rare example of tetrameric nickel where each nickel(II) centers connected by three symmetrical end-on azido anions ($\mu_{1,1}\text{-N}_3$). As far our knowledge is concerned, the Ni(1)···Ni(2) separation is 2.7943(4) Å, which shortest among the similar types of azido bridge tetranuclear nickel compound reported so far^{16–18}. Each nickel(II) centers is highly distorted octahedral (Fig. 2) as evidenced by the range of *cis* and *trans* angles which respectively from 78.18(7)° to 101.43(8)° and 166.76(8)° to 176.29(8)°. Although we observed a large deviations of *cis* and *trans* angle around Ni(1) and Ni(2), but the variations of bond distances are not too

Table 1. Crystallographic data for the complex $[\text{Ni}_4(\text{L}2)_2(\text{N}_3)_8(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_2] \cdot 4\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$

Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{58}\text{N}_{42}\text{Ni}_4$
Formula mass	1458.20
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	$\text{P}2(1)/n$
<i>a</i> (Å)	13.5488(8)
<i>b</i> (Å)	15.4121(9)
<i>c</i> (Å)	15.4608(9)
α (deg)	90
β (deg)	98.9300(10)
γ (deg)	90
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	3189.3(3)
<i>Z</i>	2
<i>D</i> _{Calcd.} (mg m ⁻³)	1.518
<i>F</i> (000)	1504
Crystal size (mm)	0.24 × 0.21 × 0.20
<i>T</i> (K)	200(2)
μ (mm ⁻¹)	1.235
<i>R</i> 1 ^a	0.0423
<i>wR</i> 2 ^b	0.1085

$$^aR = \frac{\sum(|F_o| - |F_c|)}{\sum|F_o|}; \quad ^bWR = \frac{\{\sum w(|F_o|^2 - |F_c|^2)^2 / \sum w(|F_o|^2)\}^{1/2}}$$

Fig. 2. Highly distorted coordination sphere around Ni(1) and Ni(2) of symmetric tetranuclear compound.

high (Ni(1) : 2.0483(19) Å to 2.145(2) Å; Ni(2) : 2.052(2) Å to 2.123(2) Å). The possible reasons for this may be due to tightly attached octahedral transformed rigid (N_6) ligand (L2) (Scheme 2) ligated in the bis(didentate mode)

Table 2. Selected bond distances and bond angles for the Ni₄ complex

Bond distances (Å)			
Ni(1)-N(1A)	2.0483(19)	Ni(2)-N(21)	2.123(2)
Ni(1)-N(41)	2.054(2)	N(11)-N(12)	1.205(3)
Ni(1)-N(4A)	2.123(2)	N(12)-N(13)	1.143(3)
Ni(1)-N(11)	2.138(2)	N(21)-N(22)	1.213(3)
Ni(1)-N(21)	2.1405(19)	N(22)-N(23)	1.145(3)
Ni(1)-N(31)	2.145(2)	N(31)-N(32)	1.208(3)
Ni(1)...Ni(2)	2.7943(4)	N(32)-N(33)	1.146(3)
Ni(2)-N(6A)#1	2.057(2)	N(41)-N(42)	1.177(3)
Ni(2)-N(51)	2.090(2)	N(42)-N(43)	1.153(3)
Ni(2)-N(11)	2.0908(19)	N(51)-C(52)	1.126(3)
Ni(2)-N(3A)#1	2.1103(19)	C(52)-C(51)	1.452(4)
Ni(2)-N(31)	2.116(2)	Ni(1)...Ni(2)	2.7943(4)
Bond angles (deg)			
N(1A)-Ni(1)-N(41)	92.49(8)	N(51)-Ni(2)-N(11)	167.48(8)
N(1A)-Ni(1)-N(4A)	81.72(8)	N(6A)#1-Ni(2)-N(3A)#1	81.87(8)
N(41)-Ni(1)-N(4A)	94.69(9)	N(51)-Ni(2)-N(3A)#1	95.33(8)
N(1A)-Ni(1)-N(11)	99.15(8)	N(11)-Ni(2)-N(3A)#1	93.96(7)
N(41)-Ni(1)-N(11)	166.76(8)	N(6A)#1-Ni(2)-N(31)	97.81(9)
N(4A)-Ni(1)-N(11)	93.22(7)	N(51)-Ni(2)-N(31)	89.94(8)
N(1A)-Ni(1)-N(21)	176.29(8)	N(11)-Ni(2)-N(31)	80.90(8)
N(41)-Ni(1)-N(21)	90.47(8)	N(3A)#1-Ni(2)-N(31)	174.70(8)
N(4A)-Ni(1)-N(21)	95.80(7)	N(6A)#1-Ni(2)-N(21)	176.27(8)
N(11)-Ni(1)-N(21)	78.18(7)	N(51)-Ni(2)-N(21)	91.30(8)
N(1A)-Ni(1)-N(31)	97.33(8)	N(11)-Ni(2)-N(21)	79.60(8)
N(41)-Ni(1)-N(31)	93.17(9)	N(3A)#1-Ni(2)-N(21)	94.50(7)
N(4A)-Ni(1)-N(31)	172.11(8)	N(31)-Ni(2)-N(21)	85.88(8)
N(11)-Ni(1)-N(31)	79.17(8)	Ni(2)-N(11)-Ni(1)	82.71(7)
N(21)-Ni(1)-N(31)	84.74(8)	Ni(2)-N(21)-Ni(1)	81.89(7)
N(6A)#1-Ni(2)-N(51)	88.20(9)	Ni(2)-N(31)-Ni(1)	81.94(7)
N(6A)#1-Ni(2)-N(11)	101.43(8)		

around Ni(1) and Ni(2) centers. The only difference among the nickel centers is Ni(1) additionally connected by one terminal azide anion while that of Ni(2) by one solvent acetonitrile molecule. This change of ligational mode has no significant role towards the variations of bond distances around Ni(1) and Ni(2) centers.

IR spectroscopy :

Infrared spectra of [Ni₄(L2)₂(N₃)₈(CH₃CN)₂].4CH₃CN (**1**) exhibit bands at 2062 cm⁻¹ and 2028 cm⁻¹, respectively, corresponding to the asymmetric stretching vibrations of N₃ [*v*_{as}(N₃)] and also exhibit band at 2123 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the terminal N₃ present in the complex, which are similar to those reported¹³⁻¹⁵. The stretching

vibrations of the C=N bond of the Schiff base in the complex are 1608 and 1574 cm⁻¹, respectively.

Magnetic properties :

The magnetic properties of tetrameric nickel(II) compound [Ni₄(L2)₂(N₃)₈(CH₃CN)₂].4CH₃CN (**1**) was investigated in the temperature range 2-300 K. The temperature dependence of $\chi_M T$ (χ_M is the molar magnetic susceptibility per Ni₄ unit) of **1** in the range 300-2 K is shown in Fig. 3.

The magnetic interactions in most tetranuclear transition metal complexes have been interpreted based on the assumption that the four interaction pathways between inner and outer metal centers are equivalent. The $\chi_M T$

Fig. 3. χ_M vs T and $\chi_M T$ vs T data for $[\text{Ni}_4(\text{L}2)_2(\text{N}_3)_8(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_2]$ (**1**).

product decreases with decreasing temperature, first slightly until ~ 62 K and then sharply to reach a maximum value at 24 K. Below this temperature, the $\chi_M T$ product shows a sharp decrease. The increase before the maximum is in agreement with a dominant ferromagnetic interaction inside the Ni_4 units, whereas the decrease of $\chi_M T$ below the maximum is likely associated with the presence of magnetic anisotropy and/or weak antiferromagnetic interactions. The detail interpretation including assignments of J values is under investigation. The structural and magnetic properties of selected tri- μ_2 -1,1-azido bridged nickel(II) complexes have been tabulated below (Table 3). In the present tetrameric complex the average Ni-N-Ni angle is the lowest $\{82.2(7)$ and Ni \cdots Ni separation is the shortest

$\{2.7943(4) \text{ \AA}\}$ among the triple end-on azido bridged tetranuclear Ni^{II} complexes of this kind. It is to be noted that for triple $\mu_{1,1}$ - N_3 -bridged azido system, the Ni-N-Ni angle is important in determining the nature of coupling as predicted by Ruiz *et al.*¹⁹.

Conclusion

We have reported here a rare example of tetranuclear nickel(II) complex, $[\text{Ni}_4(\text{L}2)_2(\text{N}_3)_8(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_2].4\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ (**1**) containing triple end-on ($\mu_{1,1}$ - N_3) bridged azido anions with shortest Ni \cdots Ni separation and lowest Ni-N-Ni angle. The example could be a potential metalloligand act as bis(didentate) binding mode keeping intact of other two nitrogen atoms for further reaction towards assembling more transition metal ions to get polynuclear (homo- and hetero-metallic) with possible high-spin ground state by judicious choice of metal ions as well as bridging anions. We are currently exploring towards the possibility of synthesizing different homo- and hetero-metallic polynuclear species by using different metal ions, bridging anions and also numerous substituted derivatives of the hexadentate ligand as stated, which could eventually show SMM behaviour.

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Table 3. Structural and magnetic properties selected tri- μ_2 -1,1-azido bridged nickel(II) complexes

Compound	Ni-N-Ni ($^\circ$)	Ni \cdots Ni separation (\AA)	Ref.
$[\text{L}_2\text{Ni}(\mu\text{-}1,1\text{-N}_3)_3]$ L = 1,4,7-trimethyl-1,4,7-triazacyclononane	85.9	2.896(1)	16
(Calix) $\text{Ni}_2(\mu\text{-}1,1\text{-N}_3)_3$	86.2	2.852(2)	17
$[\text{Ni}(\text{tmeda})(\text{N}_3)_2]_n$	84.2	2.8692(7)	18 ^a
$[\text{Ni}_4(\text{L}2)_2(\text{N}_3)_8(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_2].4\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$	82.2	2.7943(4)	Present work

^a $[\text{Ni}(\text{tmeda})(\text{N}_3)_2]_n$ contains three end-on and one end-to-end bridges in alternation in a polymeric chain.

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Supplementary data

Crystallographic data of the [Ni₄(L2)₂(N₃)₈(CH₃CN)₂].4CH₃CN (**1**) complex has been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, with CCDC number 1432219.

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